

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN TRANSLATION

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Annotatsiya. Bugungi zamonaviy va texnologik rivojlangan dunyoda sun'iy intellekt hayotning barcha jabhalarida, shu jumladan tarjimada ham katta rol o'ynaydi. Ushbu tadqiqot sun'iy intellektning asosiy afzalliklari va kamchiliklarini o'rganadi. Qizig'i shundaki, sun'iy intellekt kabi muammolarni hal qiluvchi vositalarga kirish imkoniyati bilan yangi ma'lumotlarni olish, muammolarni hal qilish, inson ish jarayonlarini takomillashtirish va ijodkorlikni oshirish osonlashdi, ammo uning salbiy tomonlari ham bor, bular xavfsizlik xatarlari, ijodkorlikning yetishmasligi va inson ko'nikmalarining rivojlanishining pasayishi. Bundan tashqari, sun'iy intellekt ikki tomonlama bo'lgan tarjima sohasida ham qo'llaniladi. AI yordamida muhim hujjatlarni tarjima qilish ishonchli yoki professional bo'lmasligi mumkin. Zero, madaniy jihatdan nozik va autentik matnlar tarjimasi madaniyat va tarjima qilinayotgan hozirgi tilning o'ziga xos xususiyatlarini chuqur bilishni talab qiladi. Ushbu maqolada, asosan, tarjima sohasida sun'iy intellektning ijobiy va salbiy tomonlariga e'tibor qaratilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: sun'iy intellektning ta'siri, tarjimada sun'iy intellekt, sun'iy intellektning afzalliklari va kamchiliklari, Chat GPT, Sun'iy intellect.

Аннотация. В современном и технологически продвинутом мире искусственный интеллект играет огромную роль во всех аспектах жизни, включая перевод. Это исследование исследует основные преимущества и недостатки искусственного интеллекта. Интересно, что с доступом к решениям проблем, таким как ИИ, стало легче получать новую информацию, решать проблемы, улучшать рабочие процессы человека и повышать креативность, однако у него также есть свои недостатки, которые включают риски безопасности, отсутствие креативности и снижение развития человеческих навыков. Кроме того, ИИ также используется в сфере перевода, которая является двусторонней. Перевод важных документов с использованием ИИ может быть ненадёжным или профессиональным. Поскольку перевод культурно чувствительных и аутентичных текстов требует глубоких знаний культуры и особенностей текущего переводимого языка. В данной работе основное внимание уделяется положительным и отрицательным сторонам искусственного интеллекта в области перевода.

Ключевые слова: влияние ИИ, ИИ в переводе, плюсы и минусы ИИ, Chat GPT, искусственный интеллект.

Annotation. In today's modern and technologically advanced world, artificial intelligence plays a huge role in all aspects of life, including translation. This study explores the major advantages and disadvantages of AI. Interestingly, with access to problem-solvers like AI, getting new information, solving problems, improving human workflows, and enhancing creativity became easier, however, it also has negatives, which are security risks, a lack of creativity, and decreased human skill development. Moreover, AI is also used in the translation sphere, which is two-sided. Translating essential papers with the use of AI may not be reliable or professional. Since translation of culturally sensitive and authentic texts requires deep knowledge of culture and

the peculiarities of the current language being translated. This paper mainly focuses on the positives and negatives of AI in the translation field.

Keywords: *influence of AI, AI in translation, Pros and cons of AI, Chat GPT, Artificial intelligence.*

Nowadays, with the rapid growth of technology, AI, including Chat gpt becoming more and more advanced. Over the past few decades, AI has developed gradually; now it is used in almost all fields. Particularly, the development of artificial intelligence also affected the sphere of translation. It has greatly revolutionized the translation industry by enabling affordable, quick translations, providing individuals with qualitative search engines. AI search engines like Chat GPT and Google Translate are used frequently to translate articles, texts, and papers. And there is growing concern about the reliability of translated material by machine because of a lack of cultural and contextual awareness. As machine often fails to recognize idioms, metaphors, and cultural terms, this can lead to offensive results. However, AI translation develops day by day, and offers convenience for individuals and business organisations. The innovation of AI in translation is revolutionizing the way we communicate across languages, making translation more accessible for everyone.

“The concept of “artificial intelligence” goes back thousands of years, to ancient philosophers. In those times, inventors created a thing called “automatons,” which were mechanical and moved independently without help. The word “automaton” comes from Greek and means “acting of one's own will”. Artificial intelligence was officially founded as an academic discipline in 1956, and the field went through multiple cycles of optimism throughout its history, including periods of loss of funding. The period of rapid growth of AI, also called as “AI boom,” was from 1980 to 1987. This happened mainly because of research, and additional government funding to support researchers. For example, in 1980, the first conference of the AI was held at Stanford, and then after a year in 1981, the Japanese government allocated 850\$ million (over 2\$ billion in today’s money) to the Fifth Generation Computer project. Their goal was to invent computers that could translate, converse in human language”(Tableau,2025,para.2). Nowadays development of artificial intelligence is huge. For instance, as AI improves language skills, AI systems are getting a better understanding of human nature and using human language. And this makes tools like Chabots and virtual assistants more useful. Enhanced vision for AI that can generate people and animals as real.

ADVANTAGES OF AI TRANSLATION

Technological innovation has reshaped the field of translation. To be more precise, with artificial tools like Chat GPT, artificial assistants, the translation processes become easier. The reason these tools are very hands-on and fast. According to Ma “Artificial intelligence translation is to translate a written or sound form of a natural language into another written or sound form of another natural language based on a specific computer program which combines the knowledge of computer linguistics, artificial intelligence, and mathematical logic” (2020,p.133). Moreover, AI translation involves linguistic capabilities that could be considered as natural language understanding, natural language generation, summarization, and analysis. For instance, combining speech recognition, a mobile application like Google Assistant translates spoken Russian into spoken English in real time. According to Rui, although Chat GPT is primarily built for broad language comprehension and production. Its strong linguistic abilities make it sustainable for translation purposes. (Rui,2024,p.42). Additionally, another advantage of AI translation is

affordability, since most artificial engines often do not require a fee. Thus, translating material with AI is more effective and affordable. As Ma mentioned, artificial intelligence translation has been widely used and popularized because of its advantages of low cost, high degree of automation, fast translation speed, easy operation, and budget saving. (Ma,2020,p.134).

DISADVANTAGES OF AI TRANSLATION

Despite the benefits of AI translation, there are some issues related to translating material. First and foremost is a lack of context understanding. Since artificial engines tend to fail on text that includes metaphors, idioms, and cultural nuances, translated material might turn out incorrect. It may lead to misunderstandings and offensive results. Alsalem suggests that a drawback of using this technology is that it frequently generates translations that lack context, are irrelevant, and are even absurd. (2019, p.49). Moreover, over-reliance on artificial intelligence in translation may lead to negative results for people, because dependence on Chat GPT or Google Translate reduces the demand for human interpreters and accordingly diminishes human linguistic skills. Alsalem (2019) states that dependence on editing Google translation does not assist translation newcomers to grow into a professional interpreter any more than overreliance warming pre-cooked meals might help in becoming a chef.

In conclusion, artificial intelligence has undoubtedly changed the field of translation in many ways, offering a lot of advantages that make AI an invaluable tool in today's world. While there are some nuances with specific and authentic vocabulary, in the nearest future, AI technology promises more accurate and culturally-aware translations. As artificial intelligence evolves, it will soon be easy for companies and businesses to collaborate with not only local corporations but also worldwide organizations. Finally, due to the accessibility of AI translation engines, everyone can overcome language barriers, communicate with people from different countries, and travel more confidently.

REFERENCES

1. Alsalem,R.(2019).The effects of the use of Google translate on translation students learning outcomes,46-60. <http://dx.doi.org/10.24093/awejtls/vol3no4.5>
2. Rui,S.(2024).Evaluating the translation accuracy of chat gpt and deepl through the lens of implied subjects,41-53. <http://dx.doi.org/10.24093/awejtls/vol8no4.5>
3. Ma,Y.(2020).Practice of information technology in translation teaching at Chinese regional universities in the era of artificial intelligence,132-142. <http://dx.doi.org/10.46827/ejes.v7i10.3285>
4. Tableau.(2025).What is the history of artificial intelligence(AI)? <https://www.tableau.com/data-insights/ai/history>.